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Charting a Future for Entomological Taxonomy in New Zealand

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Abstract

There is an increasing need for the identification and monitoring of insects. However, funding for entomological taxonomy, which traditionally provides the knowledge and tools for insect identification is in decline. Here, I review the history of entomological taxonomy in New Zealand and argue that the funding decline is a consequence of two broad shifts in biology. First, taxonomists test hypotheses in a qualitative manner unlike much of biology which has become increasingly quantitative. Second, there has been a shift in biology away from studying patterns and towards understanding processes and mechanisms. These scientific transformations have left the practice of taxonomy intellectually isolated from much of modern biology and led to its devaluing. I advocate for broadening taxonomy beyond the Linnaean system and to include genetic and genomic methods for identifying evolutionary lineages. This New Zealand Tree of Life would be comprised of ‘preliminary species hypotheses’ that can later be robustly tested with diverse character data and incorporated into the Linnean classification if resources and capability become available. Preliminary species hypotheses as well as associated genomic, DNA barcode, and specimen image data will support portable technologies that allow anyone to identify insects for environmental monitoring and biosecurity. This democratisation of insect identification has the potential to help build support for collections and taxonomic research. A concerted effort to accelerate the digitisation of collection data, especially genomic, DNA barcode, and specimen image data, will be necessary for implementation.

Keywords: Linnean, classification, nomenclature, species concepts, collections

Introduction

The rate of environmental change is increasing. Global trade flows, mass tourism, immigration, and climate change are driving the movement of insects worldwide at an ever-increasing pace (Turner et al. 2021; Fenn-Moltu et al. 2023). Insect pests, which include vectors of human and livestock diseases as well as agricultural pests, pose a growing threat to economies and societies. Detection and identification of insects are critical to mitigate this threat. Additionally, insects provide numerous ecosystem services such as pollination, nutrient cycling and natural pest suppression (Noriega et al. 2018; Elizalde et al. 2020). Globally, evidence is accumulating that insect communities are in decline (Outhwaite et al. 2022), threatening these services. However, these trends are debated in part because insects are difficult to identify and quantify in the environment (Saunders et al. 2020).

Within New Zealand, many insect species are endangered (Watts et al. 2012; Lester et al. 2014), but for most species we have no idea of their conservation status because they are difficult to detect and identify (Leschen et al. 2012; Lester et al. 2014; Connolly & Ward 2020). The need for rapid and accurate insect identification has never been greater (van Klink et al. 2022; Meier et al. 2024). Despite this pressing demand, many insect species within New Zealand, and indeed globally, cannot be identified because the underlying taxonomic research is incomplete.

The New Zealand insect fauna is disharmonic, with some typically low-diversity groups overseas being exceptionally diverse in New Zealand (Watt 1975b). Conversely, some groups that are hyperdiverse on nearby landmasses, such as ants, have low diversity in New Zealand (Don 2007). The antiquity of some lineages, their relative geographic isolation, and continual and rapid geological and environmental change driving diversification have resulted in a highly endemic insect fauna (Watt 1975b; Buckley et al. 2015), including some endemic families (Watt 1974; Gibbs 1989; Early et al. 2001; Leschen et al. 2005). This high degree of endemism means that New Zealand cannot rely on the taxonomic knowledge and tools from other countries for conservation and biosecurity. The so-called ‘taxonomic impediment’ – the mismatch between the scale of taxonomic research to be done and the resources and people available to do it, is particularly acute in New Zealand (Ward & Larivière 2004).

New Zealand has a small population – meaning its number of taxonomists is small. Government investment into research and development is well below the OECD average (OECD 2023), so it is not surprising that investment in taxonomy is low. This already puts us

on the back foot in terms of tackling the taxonomic impediment. Indeed, the expertise is wafer thin with usually a maximum of one practising taxonomist per major insect group, with many small orders not represented or hyperdiverse orders covered by only a single taxonomist. Furthermore, the funding per scientist is insufficient to sustain a full-time research programme in taxonomy, with funding shortfalls filled by research projects on other aspects of organismal biology. In many cases, New Zealand relies on overseas experts, funded by taxpayers from other countries, to provide taxonomic knowledge. While (like all modern science) taxonomy is a global endeavour and international collaboration is to be strongly encouraged, this is non-strategic in that we allow our taxonomically dependent outcomes to be subject to funding and employment decisions made in other countries. Outsourcing research needs is therefore not a viable solution to the taxonomic impediment in New Zealand.

Over recent decades, there have been numerous calls to increase funding for taxonomic research and to support natural history collections in New Zealand (Halloy 1995; Penman 1995; Lester et al. 2014; Nelson et al. 2015; Ward et al. 2015; Bradford-Grieve 2016; Leschen et al. 2016; Gill 2021). These calls largely use the same arguments as international perspectives (Wheeler et al. 2004; de Carvalho et al. 2007; Wägele et al. 2011; Löbl et al. 2023). Domestic efforts to garner support for increased funding may have resulted in temporary boosts, but they have not yielded substantial funding increases. While acknowledging previous efforts to advocate for increased taxonomic funding, it is essential to more deeply explore the reasons behind taxonomic funding levels before charting a way forward.

Here, I briefly review the history of entomological taxonomy in New Zealand and document the development of the science, its associated natural history collections, and the more recent erosion of support. I then explore the underlying reasons why taxonomy has lost value in the eyes of the wider biological research community and funding agencies. I argue that taxonomy needs to expand its scope beyond building the Linnean classification system and include approaches that can relatively rapidly provide a framework for investigating the complete breadth of insect diversity. Finally, I discuss the role of collection digitisation (in the broad sense of providing digital records of specimen labels, nomenclature, images, and DNA sequences) in reaching these goals and the future of insect identification. This perspective is intended to stimulate debate on the future of New Zealand taxonomic research and natural history collections. While I focus on entomology, some of these arguments are applicable to other areas of taxonomy, especially those that deal with hyperdiversity. I also focus on the

science of ‘taxonomy’ as opposed to the wider field of ‘systematics’. Here I use the common definition of ‘taxonomy’ as the science of building classifications of organisms. ‘Systematics’ is broader than taxonomy, and includes the nature of relationships among taxa, the resolution of evolutionary history and biological diversity through space and time.

This paper focuses on research to build the Linnean classification system and the large natural history collections that both depend on and support taxonomy. Natural history collections and the Linnaean system emerged from the science that developed in Europe following the Renaissance and accelerated during European colonisation and empire building in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. Māori, the indigenous people of New Zealand, have their own biological classification system developed over centuries of living in New Zealand as well as their own aspirations for the preservation and appropriate use of this system. This has been reviewed and discussed by previous authors (Haami & Roberts 2002; Rire 2012; Stewart 2024) and so will not be discussed further in this paper.

A brief history of entomological taxonomy in New Zealand

In 1769–1770, the naturalists on Captain Cook’s ship *Endeavour* collected the first New Zealand insect specimens that were deposited into a natural history collection for taxonomic research (Andrews & Gibbs 1989). Species descriptions based on these specimens were published by Fabricius (1775) (Figure 1) and these scientifically and culturally important specimens are today held in the Natural History Museum, London. The first New Zealand insect specimen that is still retained in a New Zealand taxonomic collection is a female wētāpunga or giant wētā (*Deinacrida heteracantha*), collected near Paihia, Bay of Islands in 1839 (Early 2016). Insect collecting for taxonomic research was initially slow in the mid-19th century but grew along with the increasing European population. Notable and productive entomological taxonomists based in New Zealand in the late 19th and early 20th centuries were Thomas Broun (Coleoptera), Alfred Philpott (Lepidoptera), George Hudson (Lepidoptera and other orders), William Maskell (Coccoidea), and Frederick Hutton (various orders). Taxonomists based in Europe, especially Great Britain, also described large numbers of New Zealand species at this time, in particular Edward Meyrick (Lepidoptera), Francis Walker (Lepidoptera), Francis Pascoe (Coleoptera), and David Sharp (Coleoptera). Some of these authors, particularly Broun, published large numbers of species names and descriptions in the late 19th and early 20th centuries (Figure 1). In the case of Broun, later research revealed

many names to be synonyms (e.g., Larochelle & Larivière 2001; Leschen & Buckley 2015; Larochelle & Larivière 2021).

Figure 1. The number of new insect species described each year from 1775 to 2022. Data are taken from the New Zealand Organisms Register (<https://www.nzor.org.nz/>, accessed 10th June 2024).

In addition to those describing species, there were numerous collectors, for example Richard Helms (Godley 2001) and Richard Fereday (Johns 1993), who passed insect specimens onto taxonomists both in New Zealand and overseas and therefore played an indispensable role in the taxonomic process (Watts et al. 2012). These researchers and collectors laid the groundwork for the modern natural history collections in New Zealand as well as the classification of New Zealand insects. However, the late 19th century also saw many insect specimens sent to European collections, particularly London, Paris and Vienna, where they were studied by European taxonomists, and in most cases are retained in those collections to this day (Watt 1977). The transfer of insect specimens out of New Zealand was done because Europe and North America were then seen as the global centres of taxonomy. Furthermore, in the late 19th century New Zealand lacked the large public institutions to host, curate, and care for these collections and had only a very small taxonomic community. A significant example was the Broun collection of New Zealand Coleoptera type specimens,

which in 1922 was bequeathed to the Natural History Museum, London, despite the efforts of New Zealand scientists at the time to retain it in the country (Watt 1982b).

The early 20th century saw the expansion of insect collections within formal institutions rather than the private collections of the late 19th century (Lowe 1973; Watt 1982b). The early 1930s and 1940s saw drops in the rate of species descriptions (Figure 1), probably due to the Great Depression and World War II. However, activity rebounded and in the mid-20th century a well-established community of taxonomists was publishing frequent descriptions and revisions of New Zealand insects. There were numerous taxonomists employed at the Department of Scientific and Industrial Research, the National Museum of New Zealand, regional museums, government departments, and within the universities; as well as amateurs (Brownsey 1985). These decades also saw large-scale collecting across New Zealand by teams of entomologists, including less accessible areas such as offshore islands (Woodward 1954; Watt 1962, 1975a, 1982a) and remote alpine areas (Dugdale & Fleming 1978), leading to a large expansion in size and taxonomic scope of insect collections.

The post-war decades saw year-to-year variations in the numbers of new species described, as individual revisions introduced large numbers of new names, but no long-term trend is discernible. The rate of species descriptions never reached the extremes of the late 19th and early 20th centuries (Figure 1). This probably reflects the considerable effort on redescribing species but also the increased amount of data required for each new species description as not only has the science advanced but the need for more non-taxonomic information has increased (Sangster & Luksenburg 2015). For example, modern species descriptions also typically aim to provide a holistic account of a species and its biology, including geographical distribution, variation of individuals, associations with other species (e.g. plant or animal hosts), but also provide a dichotomous key and images to distinguish similar species and perhaps molecular data and phylogenetic placement. This is far more comprehensive than a vague description based on a few lines of text which was typical for descriptions published in the 19th and early 20th centuries.

Despite this productivity there is still a significant taxonomic impediment in New Zealand entomology with approximately 4,000 to 5,800 undescribed insect species (MacFarlane et al. 2010). Taking a mean post-war rate of 69 new species described per year (Figure 1) it will take between 59 and 85 years to describe all these unknown species. Furthermore, this is only part of the picture: many of the species described in the 19th and early 20th centuries require revision and redescription. Recent revisions often contain at least as many revised, synonymised species as newly described species (Leschen & Buckley 2015;

Larochelle & Larivière 2021; Dugdale et al. 2023). Generic concepts also need revision to ensure they are monophyletic and scientifically meaningful. Therefore, a reasonable estimate is that the task of producing a complete description of the insect fauna could be at least a century away at the current rate of progress.

Why has funding for taxonomy declined?

It is commonly asserted that funding for taxonomy is in decline globally (Agnarsson & Kuntner 2007; Engel et al. 2021; Löbl et al. 2023). There is evidence this is the case in New Zealand although comprehensive temporal data across the sector are hard to come by. A survey from 1985 reported 17 specialist entomological systematists employed in New Zealand (Brownsey 1985), whereas a casual review of institutions today indicates the number is currently less than this. Penman (1995) claimed a halving in systematics capability nationally in the 20 years to 1995. Nelson et al. (2015) reported that surveys of collection-holding institutions showed a drop in collection-focused work between 1995/1996 and 2001. A 2019 government review claimed funding was currently 'static' (Anonymous 2019). The budget allocation for Nationally Significant Collections and Databases (which excludes museums and university-hosted collections, and includes some non-taxonomic collections) was NZ\$19 million per annum in 2019 (Anonymous 2019), although it had increased to NZ\$22 million per annum by 2024 (Anonymous 2024b). This represents a 15.8% increase despite there being 28.4% wage inflation during this period (Anonymous 2024a).

Why has this decline occurred and why have arguments to significantly increase funding for taxonomy been unsuccessful? The funding situation is typically attributed to two causes: 1) taxonomists are not valued or recognised (Wheeler et al. 2004; Engel et al. 2021; Löbl et al. 2023); 2) newer technologies are drawing funding away from taxonomy (Crisci 2006; Wheeler 2008; Ebach et al. 2011; Löbl et al. 2023). However, the low ascribed value and the shift in resources to newer technologies are symptoms of two deeper scientific trends (Godfray & Knapp 2004; Wheeler 2008). First, taxonomy differs from other fields of modern biology in that its method is based on qualitative hypothesis testing, whereas biology has become much more quantitative over recent decades. Second, the goal of taxonomy is to assign organisms to groups and describe these groups. The goal is to produce a description of biological patterns, whereas much of modern biology has moved away from description of

patterns and onto revealing processes and mechanisms (Wheeler 2008). To its detriment, these two trends have left taxonomy isolated from much of modern biology.

Taxonomy is concerned with classifying organisms into hierarchically arranged groups, or taxa. One of the primary objectives of taxonomy is to identify species units, which form the foundational level of the hierarchical structure of biodiversity. In that sense taxonomy is descriptive in what it is trying to achieve (the classification as a description of biodiversity patterns), but its methodology is hypothetico-deductive (Gaston & Mound 1993; Baum 1998; Hey et al. 2003; Crisci 2006; Haszprunar 2011; Pante et al. 2015; Zachos 2018). The species hypothesis makes predictions about the distribution of character state data among individuals and populations (Maddison & Whitton 2023). It is the predictions (character state distributions) that are examined by the taxonomist. No matter how robust a species classification may seem, as a hypothesis it is open to testing and falsification. If a taxonomist collects new character state data, they may consider these data to contradict the predictions implied by a previous species hypothesis. This could result in a new species being described, or a synonymy being declared to accommodate the observed character state variation. Similarly, a reinterpretation of existing character state data can also lead to falsification of a species hypothesis and subsequent nomenclatural changes. The data that taxonomists collect to test predictions of a species hypothesis depends on the taxon under study. In entomology these include characters from morphology, increasingly from DNA sequences, and in some cases behaviour and geographic distribution. This is ‘integrative taxonomy’ (Dayrat 2005): the application of multiple characters, of different types, which leads to the most powerful hypothesis tests and, therefore, the greatest confidence in the acceptance or rejection of a species hypothesis (Schlick-Steiner et al. 2010). Such species hypotheses and associated taxonomic descriptions can be thought of as ‘gold standard’ as they are likely to be highly robust and therefore of greatest use for identification and further biological studies.

Not everyone agrees with the view that taxonomy is fundamentally hypothetico-deductive. For example, Thiele et al. (2021) and Zachos (2022) have characterised taxonomy as being intermediate between the hypothetico-deductive approach and describing pattern. It is also important to note that the taxonomic name or nomenclature is distinct from the species hypothesis. The latter is part of a scientific process whereas the former is not. Choosing a particular name in entomology is a sociocultural process that follows rules set by the International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature (e.g., the Principle of Priority), and informal conventions (e.g., the etiquette of not naming a species after oneself). Confusion

between the scientific act of testing taxonomic hypotheses and the sociocultural act of naming taxa leads to the misconception that taxonomy is just about ‘giving things names’.

While taxonomists frequently refer to taxonomy as being hypothesis-driven (Haszprunar 2011), it is not in the sense that most biologists are familiar with. How taxonomy differs from many other areas of modern biology is that falsification is typically qualitative and non-statistical. There are some quantitative tests of species status (Sites & Marshall 2003; Nielsen & Matz 2006; Pons et al. 2006; Rosenberg 2007), and these are being increasingly used, but they have not been applied to most recognised species because they require genetic data, which has only been readily available since the advent of PCR in the 1990s. The reliance on qualitative hypothesis-testing stems in part from the lack of an agreed-upon, universal species concept and the disconnection between the predictions of species concepts and biological reality (De Queiroz 2007). When a species concept is proposed for a particular taxon, it is often difficult to derive ‘critical’ and ‘persuasive’ predictions (Fudge & Turko 2020) that can be applied to the observed character state data to test the species hypothesis in a quantitative manner.

Perhaps the best-known example of this problem is reproductive isolation in the context of the Biological Species Concept (Mayr 1942), where it is difficult to derive meaningful predictions when putative sister species are allopatric, which is often the case (Ehrlich 1961). Another example is the prediction of monophyly under phylogenetic or genealogical approaches to delimiting species, where large numbers of loci in the genome (and in some cases even a majority) can be non-monophyletic – even when a species has a single origin and is itself monophyletic (Degnan & Rosenberg 2006). In this situation, the key prediction is of monophyletic gene trees, yet this is not a critical or persuasive prediction for testing the hypothesis because we expect many gene trees to be non-monophyletic. There are other factors that prevent the quantitative testing of hypotheses including speciation being a continuous process, yet the Linnaean classification is comprised of discrete categories (Bock 2004; Galtier 2019; Stankowski & Ravinet 2021).

The second trend in biology that has contributed to the erosion of support and funding for taxonomy is the shift in focus from the discovery and description of biological patterns – of which taxonomy largely consists – towards understanding processes and mechanisms (Godfray & Knapp 2004; Bortolus 2008; Wheeler 2008). This is a trend that accelerated through the twentieth century due to the development of general models in biology (e.g., the ‘New Synthesis’), the development of technologies that enabled data collection to examine these models at different levels of biological organisation (e.g., electron microscopy,

molecular biology) and the growth of statistics, computational biology and powerful computers that enabled quantitative hypothesis testing. This trend is evident elsewhere in biology, in fields such as ecology, where literature reviews show a shift from describing ecological patterns to understanding processes and functions in the latter half of the 20th century (Swihart et al. 2002; Gorham & Kelly 2018). If one considers the field of systematics in its broad sense, similar trends are evident. The earliest issues of the journal *Systematic Zoology* (renamed *Systematic Biology* in 1992) from the 1950s are dominated by nomenclatural studies or opinions, whereas the journal today is almost completely devoted to phylogenetics, methods of analysis and evolutionary biology. Nomenclatural papers are exceedingly rare, and the empirical phylogenetic papers almost always use phylogenies (a pattern) to understand processes of character evolution, speciation, or biogeography.

The shift in focus within biology from pattern to process, coupled with the qualitative hypothesis testing methodology employed by taxonomists that is unfamiliar to most modern biologists, has led to the isolation of taxonomy within modern biology. Despite the critical need to identify insect species and the dependence of much of modern biology on the Linnean classification, this isolation has led to a devaluing of taxonomy and subsequent erosion of funding.

Linnean nomenclature must maintain scientific robustness

There have been numerous responses to the decline in taxonomic funding globally. These include defence of the status quo (Wheeler et al. 2004; Löbl et al. 2023), greatly minimising the information in taxonomic descriptions (Sharkey et al. 2021; Sharkey et al. 2023), introducing new technologies to scale up the rate of data collection (Hartop et al. 2022), and developing new ways of describing or categorising biodiversity (Hebert et al. 2003; Tautz et al. 2003). But which of these approaches is most likely to yield support for taxonomy from the wider scientific community and funding agencies?

Like any field of science, taxonomy is a time-consuming activity. Taxonomists have informal standards for data used to test species hypotheses. Taxonomic research includes procedures such as insect observation and collecting, specimen preparation and curation, dissection, microscopy, imaging, illustration, and DNA sequencing and analysis. This is in addition to the need to examine the historical literature to a much greater degree than most other areas of science. Furthermore, taxonomy requires the study of specimens used in

previous taxonomic publications. Critically, this includes the holotype and other type specimens, to avoid the establishment of synonymies. These types are often distant from the taxonomist, and, in the case of New Zealand, many are retained in the large European imperial collections (e.g., London, Paris, and Vienna). This is a significant impediment to New Zealand taxonomy (Watt 1982b), and indeed for many post-colonial nations.

Throughout history taxonomy has absorbed new technologies to increase the number of characters, the quality of characters, the diversity of character types (Padial et al. 2010; Friedrich et al. 2014; Wang et al. 2016; Wipfler et al. 2016; Salili-James et al. 2023) as well as enhancing the dissemination of taxonomic outputs and tools (Johnson 2007; Wheeler 2010; Page 2023). Nevertheless, there is ongoing pressure to increase the pace of taxonomic study to overcome the taxonomic impediment. In response to this pressure there is a movement to reduce the information in taxonomic descriptions so the goal can be reached much more quickly. This is the *minimalist revision approach* of Sharkey et al. (2021) who described 403 new species of braconid wasps with few to no morphological characters but with DNA barcode data for all species. This approach will certainly increase the rate which taxonomic descriptions are produced, but in the context of qualitative hypothesis testing this is equivalent to collecting fewer data points per species hypothesis and, therefore, the test of each species hypothesis has lower power. The shortcomings of this approach have been covered by other authors (Fernandez-Triana 2022; Meier et al. 2022).

Like any field of science, it is important that Linnean taxonomy is scientifically robust (Lee 2004). In this context robustness means the qualitative test of the species hypothesis needs to have low sensitivity to varying assumptions made by different species concepts and the type and amount of character data. This robustness cannot be achieved when reducing the size of character data sets as advocated under the minimalist revision approach (Hartop et al. 2022). If we want robust species hypotheses, then large numbers of characters will continue to be needed. There are technologies emerging that promise to greatly increase the rate of data collection without sacrificing scientific robustness. The approach adopting these technologies is known as *large-scale integrative taxonomy* (Hartop et al. 2022; Salili-James et al. 2023; Karbstein et al. 2024). Briefly, this approach comprises two steps. First, high throughput methods are used to collect character data and perform a provisional grouping of specimens into putative species. Second, another character type, with a high *a priori* probability of being incongruent with the first character set, is used to test those putative species (Hartop et al. 2022). A key feature is the use of technology to accelerate the rate and scale of data collection.

Regardless of whether the large-scale integrative taxonomic framework is used or not, taxonomy must continue to adopt and standardise the technologies for accelerating the rate of character data collection. Yet even with these technological advances a complete taxonomic description of the entire New Zealand insect fauna is beyond what is possible in a reasonable time frame, given the constraints on domestic science funding. Moreover, this is also the situation even in well-funded overseas research systems. The situation for New Zealand insects is bad enough without considering other highly diverse invertebrate groups, microscopic eukaryotes and fungi (Gordon 2009; Johnston 2010; Gordon 2013). As argued by Godfray (2002) it seems futile to keep arguing to fund a goal that is only achievable decades or centuries into the future or with an historically unprecedented increase in funding and capability. Therefore, the goal needs to be reimagined so that it is achievable within the usual time frames considered in public policy (Godfray 2002).

Expanding taxonomy beyond Linnean classification

It was frustration from outside of taxonomy, with the slow progress towards completion of the Linnean classification and the inability to identify all species, which led to the proposal of DNA barcoding (Hebert et al. 2003). It is, however, important to differentiate between tools to increase the rate of taxonomic research and tools for species identification. DNA barcoding has power as an identification tool and is now, for example, becoming routine for the detection and identification of invasive species (Armstrong & Ball 2005; Madden et al. 2019) and also for inventories and surveys of biodiversity (Schmidt et al. 2015; Ferreira et al. 2024).

DNA barcoding has less utility as a tool to test species hypotheses because the data represent a single character system (Will et al. 2005). However, DNA barcoding efforts need to increase because they provide useful data for identification. However, data are also required that can resolve evolutionary and / or reproductively isolated lineages, which are the basis of most species concepts (Cracraft 1983; Mallet 1995; Haami & Roberts 2002; Sites & Marshall 2003; De Queiroz 2007; Seifert 2020). The goal is not to replace the Linnean system, or to lower its scientific robustness, but to provide a framework for describing biodiversity more quickly than Linnean taxonomy can. DNA data can characterise lineages that, in turn, can be considered as ‘preliminary species hypotheses’. These hypothesised species can be tested, verified, and described by taxonomists later if resources become available. In the meantime, these hypothesised species can be used as a basis in downstream

conservation actions or ecological studies that require biodiversity to be divided into scientifically meaningful entities. However, it must be remembered that these hypothesised species have not been subject to robust testing and, therefore, any downstream inference will not be as reliable as that from a fully revised taxon.

In the context of New Zealand insects, the goal should be to collect genetic information by dense taxonomic sampling of all orders. This must be driven by taxonomists, where there is local capability, who understand the potential taxonomic diversity within a group. This effort needs to include DNA barcoding, as an identification tool, as well as genome skimming (Maddison & Sproul 2020); it is also likely to include high-quality genome assemblies as the technologies cheapen. Specimens must be accessioned into a publicly funded collection, accessible online with images and fully digitised label data. Once morphological characters are collected these data then become amenable to large-scale integrative taxonomy (Hartop et al. 2022). The genetic data can be used to build ‘preliminary species hypotheses’. However, these entities should not be given formal Linnean binomials, as the data are insufficient for robustly testing species hypotheses. These categories could also replace the over-used tag-names in New Zealand taxonomy, which are non-scientific because they are typically used with no published (or, at least, publicly available) data to test their veracity (Leschen et al. 2009). In terms of qualitative hypothesis-testing, these ‘preliminary species hypotheses’ sit below the ‘gold standard’ species hypotheses that form the basis of the Linnean classification. It is worth noting that similar approaches are standard within mycology (Koljalg et al. 2020; Lücking et al. 2021) and bacteriology (Parks et al. 2018) and there will be aspects from these taxonomic systems that can be lifted over into zoology.

This goal, a ‘New Zealand Tree of Life’, is likely achievable within 5 – 10 years with moderate investment and mobilisation of local and overseas natural history collections. Methods are now available for obtaining DNA barcode data from 100s to 1000s of specimens in single DNA sequencing runs (Dopheide et al. 2022; Hartop et al. 2022). Large-scale collection of whole genome data from pinned insect specimens is also becoming routine (Parejo et al. 2020; Korlevic et al. 2021; Hsiao et al. 2023; He et al. 2024). Therefore, any initiative needs to be established such that it can transition between technologies as the DNA sequencing price points reach more affordable levels. There are several international models such as the Darwin Tree of Life (<https://www.darwintreeoflife.org/>) that provide good frameworks, and associated data collection, analysis and management pipelines.

The increasing amount of environmental DNA (eDNA) data (Drummond et al. 2015; Watts et al. 2019; Hermans et al. 2022) can be mined for insect Operational Taxonomic Units

(OTUs). These OTUs are not derived from DNA sequencing specimens and do not have a physical reference specimen. Therefore, it is difficult to reconcile these OTUs with other types of character data. From a hypothesis testing perspective these OTUs can also be considered ‘preliminary species hypotheses’, but with a weaker degree of support than from specimen-based DNA sequencing approaches (as outlined earlier). This approach will require a large-scale eDNA survey of New Zealand, focusing on the sampling of soil, water, air, and insect trap residues. Achieving this goal would also be a 5- to 10 year project with a moderate financial investment. The output would be a comprehensive database of OTUs that, over time, could be connected to described species or to DNA sequences obtained from individual specimens. This goal should be phased so that the ‘New Zealand Tree of Life’ described above is available as a comparative framework for the eDNA-derived OTUs.

What is the future role of Linnean taxonomy? In science there are times when robust hypothesis-testing is necessary because a high degree of confidence is required in those hypotheses before proceeding with downstream research or management actions. In the context of taxonomy, we need to have high confidence in a species hypothesis when that species is endangered, and funding is being dedicated to its conservation. Similarly, in biosecurity settings we need to have confidence in classification and associated identification tools when intercepting insects at the border and determining whether they belong to species of high biosecurity risk. It is these groups of species, where the highest degree of scientific robustness is required, on which Linnean taxonomy must focus. It is important to note that these priorities will shift over time.

Some might propose a zero-sum argument in response to this proposal and claim it will draw funding away from Linnean taxonomy. There is of course a risk in this, but this needs to be weighed against the risk of the status quo, which is the incremental building of the Linnean classification, that shows no sign of attracting increased funding. It is also important that taxonomists take ownership of different approaches to describing biodiversity, and that these approaches be considered as part of taxonomy, *sensu lato*, yet distinct from Linnean taxonomy. Some will also claim this reframing of taxonomy denigrates the decades of preceding taxonomic research. This is not the case. The practice of science and the expectations placed on scientists by society are always changing and taxonomy is not and should not be immune to these pressures. The agenda presented here builds on 250 years of developing the Linnean classification of New Zealand insects and would not be possible without this enormously valuable scientific contribution. Furthermore, the organismal biological knowledge that taxonomists possess will be essential. The intent is to better

position taxonomy to succeed given changing technologies and expectations from outside the field and outside science.

The future of insect identification and the critical role of collection digitisation

The demand for taxonomic information to support real-time environmental monitoring and biosecurity risk assessment is rapidly increasing. Consequently, the traditional approaches to insect sampling and identification will increasingly not be tenable and need to adapt. Traditional approaches will also be compounded by the likely shortage of expert diagnosticians as funding decreases and the ageing workforce is not replaced upon retirement. New technologies, including portable technologies, are being developed for immediate species detection and identification. These present a tremendous opportunity for taxonomy, but the opportunity must be embraced. These include DNA barcoding for identifying individual species (Hebert et al. 2003; Antil et al. 2023), eDNA for assessing whole communities (Bierman & Lloyd 2024), and automated image recognition for specimen sorting and identification (Arje et al. 2020; Hoyer et al. 2021; Wüthrich et al. 2022). The latter technology has promise as an identification tool, particularly because (unlike DNA barcoding) it does not depend on a single locus; and also, because (depending on the implementation) it currently requires less physical technology (Brydegaard et al. 2024). Automated image recognition of individual macro-insects can often require only a smartphone, appropriate app and possibly an internet connection, although the technology for the generation of DNA barcodes is currently undergoing miniaturisation (Green et al. 2017; Srivathsan et al. 2024). Data analysis pipelines are also emerging that integrate DNA barcodes and images for specimen identification (Blair et al. 2024), thereby leveraging the benefits of both technologies. Environmental DNA will become another critical driver and opportunity for taxonomy following the expansion of this tool for species detection and environmental monitoring in New Zealand (Holdaway et al. 2017; Bulman et al. 2018; Watts et al. 2019; Wilkinson et al. 2024). Whatever the individual pros and cons of these tools, it is expected that they will begin to supplant traditional methods of insect identification and the subsequent applications of detection and monitoring (Brydegaard et al. 2024; Meier et al. 2024).

All these technologies will be able to identify specimens of both Linnean species and ‘preliminary species hypotheses’ defined by genetic information. In the case of eDNA, these

entities will be able to be detected in the environment. These technologies, particularly automated image recognition, promise to democratise insect identification by making it accessible to non-specialists. This presents a great opportunity for taxonomy because the science will increase in value as more people are able to detect and identify insect species (Hulcr et al. 2023). However, for these technologies to be successfully transitioned, large-scale collection of specimen data is required. Supporting portable insect identification tools will require digitised specimen records, up-to-date nomenclature, georeferenced data, and most critically images, and DNA sequences. For this reason collection digitisation is an absolute priority (Hulcr et al. 2023). In most science systems, and certainly in New Zealand, labour is by far the biggest cost. Any significant increase in data collection will have to rely on new technologies, such as robotics (Wüthrich et al. 2022). It is important to consider where the bottlenecks are in data generation and alleviate these (e.g., Ang et al. 2013; Tegelberg et al. 2014; Hudson et al. 2015; Short et al. 2018; Salili-James et al. 2023). Citizen science will also play a role by providing locality records and perhaps more importantly, specimen images to help train image recognition algorithms.

Conclusions

The decline in taxonomic funding is a result of the practice of taxonomy becoming isolated from modern biology due both to its qualitative hypothesis-testing method, and to the shift in biology away from understanding patterns to focusing on process and mechanism. To overcome this erosion of status and support, entomological taxonomy in New Zealand needs to move from advocating for the completion of the Linnean classification as its primary goal and present goals that are achievable with realistic funding levels and timescales. This can be accomplished by broadening taxonomy beyond Linnean classification. Genetic data are able to rapidly characterise evolutionary lineages that can be considered ‘preliminary species hypotheses’. These hypotheses can later be robustly tested with diverse character data and subsequently incorporated into the Linnean classification. This approach is preferable to reducing the robustness of Linnean taxonomy through minimalist revisions, as some have advocated. The approach proposed here maintains the scientific robustness of Linnean taxonomy while simultaneously and rapidly providing entities, with a scientific basis, that can be used for identification and downstream biological research. Implementation will require large-scale collection digitisation of genomic, DNA barcode data, and specimen images.

These data will support emerging, portable technologies for insect identification based on genetic data and automated image recognition. These tools will eventually allow anyone to identify insects for environmental monitoring and biosecurity. The democratisation of insect identification will greatly increase the number of people who use taxonomic tools and help build support to enable taxonomy and collections to thrive into the 21st century.

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References

- Agnarsson I, Kuntner M 2007. Taxonomy in a changing world: Seeking solutions for a science in crisis. *Systematic Biology* 56(3): 531-539.
- Andrews JRH, Gibbs GW 1989. The first New Zealand insects collected on Cook's *Endeavour* voyage. *Pacific Science* 43(1): 102-114.
- Ang Y, Puniamoorthy J, Pont AC, Bartak M, Blanckenhorn WU, Eberhard WG, Puniamoorthy N, Silva VC, Munari L, Meier R 2013. A plea for digital reference collections and other science-based digitization initiatives in taxonomy: Sepsidnet as exemplar. *Systematic Entomology* 38(3): 637-644.
- Anonymous 2019. Scientific Collections and Databases Review: Update Report. 32 p.
- Anonymous 2024a. Inflation Calculator. Retrieved 17 June 2024
<https://www.rbnz.govt.nz/monetary-policy/about-monetary-policy/inflation-calculator>
- Anonymous 2024b. Nationally Significant Collections and Databases. Retrieved 16 June 2024
<https://www.mbie.govt.nz/science-and-technology/science-and-innovation/funding-information-and-opportunities/investment-funds/strategic-science-investment-fund/funded-infrastructure/nationally-significant-collections-and-databases>
- Antil S, Abraham JS, Sripoorna S, Maurya S, Dagar J, Makhija S, Bhagat P, Gupta R, Sood U, Lal R and others 2023. DNA barcoding, an effective tool for species identification: a review. *Molecular Biology Reports* 50(1): 761-775.
- Arje J, Melvad C, Jeppesen MR, Madsen SA, Raitoharju J, Rasmussen MS, Iosifidis A, Tirronen V, Gabbouj M, Meissner K and others 2020. Automatic image-based identification and biomass estimation of invertebrates. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 11(8): 922-931.
- Armstrong KF, Ball SL 2005. DNA barcodes for biosecurity: invasive species identification. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B-Biological Sciences* 360(1464): 2373-2373.
- Baum DA 1998. Individuality and the existence of species through time. *Systematic Biology* 47(4): 641-653.
- Bierman A, Lloyd M 2024. Metabarcoding and eDNA for Insect Conservation. In: Pryke JS, Samways MJ, New TR, Cardoso P, Gaigher R ed. *Routledge Handbook of Insect Conservation*. London, Taylor and Francis. Pp. 487-500.
- Blair JD, Weiser MD, Siler CD, Kaspari M, Smith SN, McLaughlin JF, Marshall KE 2024. A hybrid approach to invertebrate biomonitoring using computer vision and DNA metabarcoding. *bioRxiv*.
- Bock WJ 2004. Species: the concept, category and taxon. *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research* 42(3): 178-190.
- Bortolus A 2008. Error cascades in the biological sciences: The unwanted consequences of using bad taxonomy in ecology. *Ambio* 37(2): 114-118.
- Bradford-Grieve J 2016. Is there a taxonomic crisis? *New Zealand Science Review* 73(3-4): 83-86.
- Brownsey PJ 1985. *Biological Systematics in New Zealand: A Report Prepared for the Systematics Association of New Zealand (SYSTANZ)*. 16 p.
- Brydegaard M, Pedales RD, Feng V, Yamoah AS, Kouakou B, Månefjord H, Wüthrich L, Pylatiuk C, Amorim DD, Meier R 2024. Towards global insect biomonitoring with frugal methods. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B-Biological Sciences* 379(1904).
- Buckley TR, Krosch M, Leschen RAB 2015. Evolution of New Zealand insects: summary and prospectus for future research. *Austral Entomology* 54(1): 1-27.

- Bulman SR, McDougal RL, Hill K, Lear G 2018. Opportunities and limitations for DNA metabarcoding in Australasian plant-pathogen biosecurity. *Australasian Plant Pathology* 47(5): 467-474.
- Connolly S, Ward D 2020. Utilising museum data for comparative analysis of threatened insect species. *Journal of Insect Conservation* 24(5): 793-804.
- Cracraft J 1983. Species concepts and speciation analysis. In: Johnston RF ed. *Current Ornithology*. New York, NY, Springer. Pp. 159-187.
- Crisci JV 2006. One-dimensional systematist: Perils in a time of steady progress. *Systematic Botany* 31(1): 217-221.
- Dayrat B 2005. Towards integrative taxonomy. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 85(3): 407-415.
- de Carvalho MR, Bockmann FA, Amorim DS, Brandao CRF, de Vivo M, de Figueiredo JL, Britski HA, de Pinna MCC, Menezes NA, Marques FPL and others 2007. Taxonomic impediment or impediment to taxonomy? A commentary on systematics and the cybertaxonomic-automation paradigm. *Evolutionary Biology* 34(3-4): 140-143.
- De Queiroz K 2007. Species concepts and species delimitation. *Systematic Biology* 56(6): 879-886.
- Degnan JH, Rosenberg NA 2006. Discordance of species trees with their most likely gene trees. *PLoS Genetics* 2(5): 762-768.
- Don W 2007. *Ants of New Zealand*. Dunedin, New Zealand, Otago University Press.
- Dopheide A, Brav-Cubitt T, Podolyan A, Leschen RAB, Ward D, Buckley TR, Dhimi MK 2022. Fast-tracking bespoke DNA reference database generation from museum collections for biomonitoring and conservation. *Molecular Ecology Resources*.
- Drummond AJ, Newcomb RD, Buckley TR, Xie D, Dopheide A, Potter BCM, Heled J, Ross HA, Tooman L, Grosser S and others 2015. Evaluating a multigene environmental DNA approach for biodiversity assessment. *Gigascience* 4.
- Dugdale JS, Fleming CA 1978. New Zealand cicadas of genus *Maoricicada* (Homoptera: Tibicinidae). *New Zealand Journal of Zoology* 5(2): 295-340.
- Dugdale JS, Emmerson AW, Hoare RJB 2023. *Declana* and *Ipana* (Insecta: Lepidoptera: Geometridae: Ennominae). *Fauna of New Zealand* 82: 1-120.
- Early JW 2016. Provenance of the type specimen of William Colenso's giant weta *Hemideina gigantea*. *Records of the Auckland Museum* 51: 49-53.
- Early JW, Masner L, Naumann ID, Austin AD 2001. Maamingidae, a new family of proctotrupoid wasp (Insecta: Hymenoptera) from New Zealand. *Invertebrate Taxonomy* 15(3): 341-352.
- Ebach MC, Valdecasas AG, Wheeler QD 2011. Impediments to taxonomy and users of taxonomy: accessibility and impact evaluation. *Cladistics* 27(5): 550-557.
- Ehrlich PR 1961. Has the Biological Species Concept outlived Its usefulness? *Systematic Zoology* 10(4): 167-176.
- Elizalde L, Arbetman M, Arnán X, Eggleton P, Leal IR, Lescano MN, Saez A, Wrenkraud V, Pirk GI 2020. The ecosystem services provided by social insects: traits, management tools and knowledge gaps. *Biological Reviews* 95(5): 1418-1441.
- Engel MS, Ceriaco LMP, Daniel GM, Dellapé PM, Löbl I, Marinov M, Reis RE, Young MT, Dubois A, Agarwal I and others 2021. The taxonomic impediment: a shortage of taxonomists, not the lack of technical approaches. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 193(2): 381-387.
- Fabricius JC 1775. *Systema Entomologiae, sistens Insectorum Classes, Ordines, Genera, Species, adjectis Synonymis, Locis, Descriptionibus, Observationibus, Kortii, Flensburgi et Lipsiae*. 832 p.

- Fenn-Moltu G, Ollier S, Bates OK, Liebhold AM, Nahrung HF, Pureswaran DS, Yamanaka T, Bertelsmeier C 2023. Global flows of insect transport and establishment: The role of biogeography, trade and regulations. *Diversity and Distributions* 29(11): 1478-1491.
- Fernandez-Triana JL 2022. Turbo taxonomy approaches: lessons from the past and recommendations for the future based on the experience with Braconidae (Hymenoptera) parasitoid wasps. *Zookeys* 1087: 199-220.
- Ferreira S, Corley MFV, Nunes J, Rosete J, Vasconcelos S, Mata VA, Verissimo J, Silva TL, Sousa P, Andrade R and others 2024. The InBIO Barcoding Initiative Database: DNA barcodes of Portuguese moths. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 12(e117169).
- Friedrich F, Matsumura Y, Pohl H, Bai M, Hörnschemeyer T, Beutel RG 2014. Insect morphology in the age of phylogenomics: innovative techniques and its future role in systematics. *Entomological Science* 17(1): 1-24.
- Fudge DS, Turko AJ 2020. The best predictions in experimental biology are critical and persuasive. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 223(19): 1-5.
- Galtier N 2019. Delineating species in the speciation continuum: A proposal. *Evolutionary Applications* 12(4): 657-663.
- Gaston KJ, Mound LA 1993. Taxonomy, Hypothesis-Testing and the Biodiversity Crisis. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B-Biological Sciences* 251(1331): 139-142.
- Gibbs GW 1989. Local or Global - Biogeography of Some Primitive Lepidoptera in New-Zealand. *New Zealand Journal of Zoology* 16(4): 689-698.
- Gill B 2021. Science and managerialism in New Zealand. *New Zealand Science Review* 77(1-2): 13-18.
- Godfray HCJ 2002. Challenges for taxonomy - The discipline will have to reinvent itself if it is to survive and flourish. *Nature* 417(6884): 17-19.
- Godfray HCJ, Knapp S 2004. Taxonomy for the twenty-first century - Introduction. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B-Biological Sciences* 359(1444): 559-569.
- Godley EJ 2001. Biographical Notes (42): Richard Helms (1842 -1914). *New Zealand Botanical Society Newsletter* 64: 39-41.
- Gordon DP 2009. *New Zealand Inventory of Biodiversity Volume 1: Kingdom Animalia Radiata, Lopotrochozoa, Deuterostomia*. Canterbury, New Zealand, Canterbury University Press. 648 p.
- Gordon DP 2013. New Zealand's genetic diversity. In: Dymond JR ed. *Ecosystem Services in New Zealand—Conditions and Trends*. Lincoln, New Zealand, Manaaki Whenua Press. Pp. 113-162.
- Gorham E, Kelly J 2018. A history of ecological research derived from titles of articles in the journal "ecology," 1925–2015. *The Bulletin of the Ecological Society of America* 99(1): 61-72.
- Green ED, Rubin EM, Olson MV 2017. The future of DNA sequencing. *Nature* 550(7675): 179-181.
- Haami B, Roberts M 2002. Genealogy as taxonomy. *International Social Science Journal* 54: 403-412.
- Halloy SR 1995. Status of New Zealand biodiversity research and resources: how much do we know? *Journal of the Royal Society of New Zealand* 25(1): 55-80.
- Hartop E, Srivathsan A, Ronquist F, Meier R 2022. Towards Large-Scale Integrative Taxonomy (LIT): Resolving the Data Conundrum for Dark Taxa. *Systematic Biology* 71(6): 1404-1422.
- Haszprunar G 2011. Species delimitations - not 'only descriptive'. *Organisms Diversity & Evolution* 11(3): 249-252.

- He SL, Su YN, Tan MK, Zwick A, Warren B, Robillard T 2024. Museomics, molecular phylogeny and systematic revision of the Eurepini crickets (Orthoptera: Gryllidae: Eneopterinae), with description of two new genera. *Systematic Entomology* 49(3): 389-411.
- Hebert PDN, Cywinska A, Ball SL, DeWaard JR 2003. Biological identifications through DNA barcodes. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B-Biological Sciences* 270(1512): 313-321.
- Hermans SM, Lear G, Buckley TR, Buckley HL 2022. Environmental DNA sampling detects between-habitat variation in soil arthropod communities, but is a poor indicator of fine-scale spatial and seasonal variation. *Ecological Indicators* 140.
- Hey J, Waples RS, Arnold ML, Butlin RK, Harrison RG 2003. Understanding and confronting species uncertainty in biology and conservation. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 18(11): 597-603.
- Holdaway RJ, Wood JR, Dickie IA, Orwin KH, Bellingham PJ, Richardson SJ, Lyver PO, Timoti P, Buckley TR 2017. Using DNA metabarcoding to assess New Zealand's terrestrial biodiversity. *New Zealand Journal of Ecology* 41(2): 251-262.
- Hoye TT, Ärje J, Bjerge K, Hansen OLP, Iosifidis A, Leese F, Mann HMR, Meissner K, Melvad C, Raitoharju J 2021. Deep learning and computer vision will transform entomology. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 118(2).
- Hsiao Y, Oberprieler RG, Zwick A, Zhou YL, Slipinski A 2023. Museomics unveil systematics, diversity and evolution of Australian cycad-pollinating weevils. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B-Biological Sciences* 290(2008).
- Hudson LN, Blagoderov V, Heaton A, Holtzhausen P, Livermore L, Price BW, van der Walt S, Smith VS 2015. Insect: Automating the Digitization of Natural History Collections. *PLoS ONE* 10(11).
- Hulcr J, Johnson AJ, Marais GC 2023. How systematic entomology will thrive in the age of artificial intelligence. *Entomology Today*, Entomological Society of America.
- Johns PM 1993. Fereday, Richard William. Retrieved 17 September 2024 <https://teara.govt.nz/en/biographies/2f5/fereday-richard-william>
- Johnson NF 2007. Biodiversity informatics. *Annual Review of Entomology* 52: 421-438.
- Johnston PR 2010. Causes and consequences of changes to New Zealand's fungal biota. *New Zealand Journal of Ecology* 34(1): 175-184.
- Karbstein K, Kösters L, Hodač L, Hofmann M, Hörandl E, Tomasello S, Wagner ND, Emerson BC, Albach DC, Scheu S and others 2024. Species delimitation 4.0: integrative taxonomy meets artificial intelligence. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*.
- Koljalg U, Nilsson HR, Schigel D, Tedersoo L, Larsson KH, May TW, Taylor AFS, Jeppesen TS, Froslev TG, Lindahl BD and others 2020. The Taxon Hypothesis Paradigm-On the Unambiguous Detection and Communication of Taxa. *Microorganisms* 8(1910).
- Korlevic P, McAlister E, Mayho M, Makunin A, Flicek P, Lawniczak MKN 2021. A Minimally Morphologically Destructive Approach for DNA Retrieval and Whole-Genome Shotgun Sequencing of Pinned Historic Dipteran Vector Species. *Genome Biology and Evolution* 13(10).
- Larochelle A, Larivière MC 2001. Carabidae (Insecta: Coleoptera): catalogue. *Fauna of New Zealand* 43: 1-285.
- Larochelle A, Larivière MC 2021. Synopsis of the tribe Platynini in New Zealand (Coleoptera: Carabidae). *Insecta Mundi* 0864: 1-96.
- Lee MSY 2004. The molecularisation of taxonomy. *Invertebrate Systematics* 18(1): 1-6.

- Leschen R, Collier K, Death R, Harding J, Smith B 2016. Systematics expertise and taxonomic status of New Zealand's freshwater insects. *New Zealand Science Review* 73(3-4): 92-95.
- Leschen RAB, Buckley TR 2015. Revision and phylogeny of *Syrphetodes* (Coleoptera: Ulodidae): implications for biogeography, alpinization and conservation. *Systematic Entomology* 40(1): 143-168.
- Leschen RAB, Lawrence JF, Slipinski SA 2005. Classification of basal Cucujoidea (Coleoptera: Polyphaga): cladistic analysis, keys and review of new families. *Invertebrate Systematics* 19(1): 17-73.
- Leschen RAB, Buckley TR, Hoare RJB 2009. The use of tag-names and New Zealand taxonomy. *New Zealand Entomologist* 32(1): 85-87.
- Leschen RAB, Marris JWM, Emberson RM, Nunn J, Hitchmough RA, Stringer IAN 2012. The conservation status of New Zealand Coleoptera. *New Zealand Entomologist* 35(2): 91-98.
- Lester PJ, Brown SDJ, Edwards ED, Holwell GI, Pawson SM, Ward DF, Watts CH 2014. Critical issues facing New Zealand entomology. *New Zealand Entomologist* 37(1): 1-13.
- Löbl I, Klausnitzer B, Hartmann M, Krell F-T 2023. The silent extinction of species and taxonomists-an appeal to science policymakers and legislators. *Diversity* 15(10): 1053.
- Lowe AD 1973. A short history of New Zealand entomology and the society. *New Zealand Entomologist* 5(2): 109-112.
- Lücking R, Aime MC, Robbertse B, Miller AN, Aoki T, Ariyawansa HA, Cardinali G, Crous PW, Druzhinina IS, Geiser DM and others 2021. Fungal taxonomy and sequence-based nomenclature (vol 6, pg 540, 2021). *Nature Microbiology* 6(7): 971-971.
- MacFarlane RP, Maddison PA, Andrew IG, Berry JA, Johns PM, Hoare RJB, Larivière M-C, Greenslade P, Henderson RC, Smithers CN and others 2010. Phylum Arthropoda, subphylum Hexapoda: Protura, springtails, diplura, and insects. *New Zealand Inventory of Biodiversity* 2: 233-467.
- Madden MJL, Young RG, Brown JW, Miller SE, Frewin AJ, Hanner RH 2019. Using DNA barcoding to improve invasive pest identification at US ports-of-entry. *PLoS ONE* 14(9): e0222291.
- Maddison DR, Sproul JS 2020. Species delimitation, classical taxonomy and genome skimming: a review of the ground beetle genus *Lionepha* (Coleoptera: Carabidae). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 189(4): 1313-1358.
- Maddison DR, Whitton J 2023. The species as a reproductive community emerging from the past. *Bulletin of the Society of Systematic Biologists* 2(1): 1-35.
- Mallet J 1995. A Species Definition for the Modern Synthesis. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 10(7): 294-299.
- Mayr E 1942. *Systematics and the Origin of Species*. New York, NY, Columbia University Press.
- Meier R, Hartop E, Pylatiuk C, Srivathsan A 2024. Towards holistic insect monitoring: species discovery, description, identification and traits for all insects. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B-Biological Sciences* 379(1904).
- Meier R, Blaimer BB, Buenaventura E, Hartop E, Rintelen T, Srivathsan A, Yeo D 2022. A re-analysis of the data in Sharkey et al.'s (2021) minimalist revision reveals that BINs do not deserve names, but BOLD Systems needs a stronger commitment to open science. *Cladistics* 38(2): 264-275.

- Nelson W, Breitwieser I, Fordyce E, Bradford-Grieve J, Penman D, Roskrug N, Trnski T, Waugh S, Webb CJ 2015. National Taxonomic Collections in New Zealand, Royal Society of New Zealand. 63 p.
- Nielsen R, Matz M 2006. Statistical approaches for DNA barcoding. *Systematic Biology* 55(1): 162-169.
- Noriega JA, Hortal J, Azcarate FM, Berg MP, Bonada N, Briones MJI, Del Toro I, Goulson D, Ibanez S, Landis DA and others 2018. Research trends in ecosystem services provided by insects. *Basic and Applied Ecology* 26: 8-23.
- OECD 2023. Gross domestic spending on R&D (indicator). Retrieved 24 May 2024 <https://data.oecd.org/rd/gross-domestic-spending-on-r-d.htm>
- Outhwaite CL, McCann P, Newbold T 2022. Agriculture and climate change are reshaping insect biodiversity worldwide. *Nature* 605(7908): 97-102.
- Padial JM, Miralles A, De la Riva I, Vences M 2010. The integrative future of taxonomy. *Frontiers in Zoology* 7: 16.
- Page R 2023. Ten years and a million links: building a global taxonomic library connecting persistent identifiers for names, publications and people. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 11: e107914.
- Pante E, Puillandre N, Viricel AE, Arnaud-Haond S, Aurelle D, Castelin M, Chenuil A, Destombe C, Forcioli D, Valero M and others 2015. Species are hypotheses: avoid connectivity assessments based on pillars of sand. *Molecular Ecology* 24(3): 525-544.
- Parejo M, Wragg D, Henriques D, Charrière JD, Estonba A 2020. Digging into the Genomic Past of Swiss Honey Bees by Whole-Genome Sequencing Museum Specimens. *Genome Biology and Evolution* 12(12): 2535-2551.
- Parks DH, Chuvochina M, Waite DW, Rinke C, Skarshewski A, Chaumeil PA, Hugenholtz P 2018. A standardized bacterial taxonomy based on genome phylogeny substantially revises the tree of life. *Nature Biotechnology* 36(10): 996-1004.
- Penman D 1995. *Biosystematics: Issues and Options for New Zealand*. Report to the Chief Scientist of the Ministry of Research, Science and Technology. 11 p.
- Pons J, Barraclough TG, Gomez-Zurita J, Cardoso A, Duran DP, Hazell S, Kamoun S, Sumlin WD, Vogler AP 2006. Sequence-based species delimitation for the DNA taxonomy of undescribed insects. *Systematic Biology* 55(4): 595-609.
- Rire JT 2012. Taxonomy - Maori whakapapa versus Western science. *International Journal of Arts and Sciences* 5(3): 59-73.
- Rosenberg NA 2007. Statistical tests for taxonomic distinctiveness from observations of monophyly. *Evolution* 61(2): 317-323.
- Salili-James A, Scott B, Livermore L, Price B, Dupont S, Hardy H, Smith VS 2023. AI-accelerated digitisation of insect collections: the next generation of Angled Label Image Capture Equipment (ALICE). *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 7: e112742.
- Sangster G, Luksenburg JA 2015. Declining Rates of Species Described per Taxonomist: Slowdown of Progress or a Side-effect of Improved Quality in Taxonomy? *Systematic Biology* 64(1): 144-151.
- Saunders ME, Janes JK, O'Hanlon JC 2020. Moving On from the Insect Apocalypse Narrative: Engaging with Evidence-Based Insect Conservation. *Bioscience* 70(1): 80-89.
- Schlick-Steiner BC, Steiner FM, Seifert B, Stauffer C, Christian E, Crozier RH 2010. Integrative Taxonomy: A Multisource Approach to Exploring Biodiversity. *Annual Review of Entomology* 55: 421-438.

- Schmidt S, Schmid-Egger C, Morinière J, Haszprunar G, Hebert PDN 2015. DNA barcoding largely supports 250 years of classical taxonomy: identifications for Central European bees (Hymenoptera, Apoidea). *Molecular Ecology Resources* 15(4): 985-1000.
- Seifert B 2020. The Gene and Gene Expression (GAGE) Species Concept: An Universal Approach for All Eukaryotic Organisms. *Systematic Biology* 69(5): 1033-1038.
- Sharkey MJ, Baker A, McCluskey K, Smith A, Naik S, Ratnasingham S, Manjunath R, Perez K, Sones J, D'Souza M 2023. Minimalist revision of *Mesochorus* Gravenhorst, 1829 (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Mesochorinae) from Área de Conservación Guanacaste, Costa Rica, with 158 new species and host records for 129 species. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 71(S2): 1-174.
- Sharkey MJ, Janzen DH, Hallwachs W, Chapman EG, Smith MA, Dapkey T, Brown A, Ratnasingham S, Naik S, Manjunath R and others 2021. Minimalist revision and description of 403 new species in 11 subfamilies of Costa Rican braconid parasitoid wasps, including host records for 219 species. *Zookeys* 1013: 1-665.
- Short AEZ, Dikow T, Moreau CS 2018. Entomological Collections in the Age of Big Data. *Annual Review of Entomology*, Vol 63 63: 513-530.
- Sites JW, Marshall JC 2003. Delimiting species: a Renaissance issue in systematic biology. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 18(9): 462-470.
- Srivathsan A, Feng V, Suárez D, Emerson B, Meier R 2024. ONTbarcoder 2.0: rapid species discovery and identification with real-time barcoding facilitated by Oxford Nanopore R10.4. *Cladistics* 40(2): 192-203.
- Stankowski S, Ravinet M 2021. Defining the speciation continuum. *Evolution* 75(6): 1256-1273.
- Stewart GT 2024. Animals of Aotearoa: Kaupapa Maori Summaries. *Anthrozoos* 37(1): 1-17.
- Swihart RK, Dunning JB, Waser PM 2002. Gray matters in ecology: dynamics of pattern, process, and scientific progress. *Bulletin of the Ecological Society of America* 83(2): 149-155.
- Tautz D, Arctander P, Minelli A, Thomas RH, Vogler AP 2003. A plea for DNA taxonomy. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 18(2): 70-74.
- Tegelberg R, Mononen T, Saarenmaa H 2014. High-performance digitization of natural history collections: Automated imaging lines for herbarium and insect specimens. *Taxon* 63(6): 1307-1313.
- Thiele KR, Conix S, Pyle RL, Barik SK, Christidis L, Costello MJ, van Dijk PP, Kirk P, Lien A, Thomson SA and others 2021. Towards a global list of accepted species I. Why taxonomists sometimes disagree, and why this matters. *Organisms Diversity & Evolution* 21(4): 615-622.
- Turner RM, Brockerhoff EG, Bertelsmeier C, Blake RE, Caton B, James A, MacLeod A, Nahrung HF, Pawson SM, Plank MJ and others 2021. Worldwide border interceptions provide a window into human-mediated global insect movement. *Ecological Applications* 31(7): e02412.
- van Klink R, August T, Bas Y, Bodesheim P, Bonn A, Fossoy F, Hoye TT, Jongejans E, Menz MHM, Miraldo A and others 2022. Emerging technologies revolutionise insect ecology and monitoring. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 37(10): 872-885.
- Wägele H, Klusmann-Kolb A, Kuhlmann M, Haszprunar G, Lindberg D, Koch A, Wägele JW 2011. The taxonomist - an endangered race. A practical proposal for its survival. *Frontiers in Zoology* 8: 25.
- Wang Y, Nansen C, Zhang YL 2016. Integrative insect taxonomy based on morphology, mitochondrial DNA, and hyperspectral reflectance profiling. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 177(2): 378-394.

- Ward DF, Larivière MC 2004. Terrestrial invertebrate surveys and rapid biodiversity assessment in New Zealand: lessons from Australia. *New Zealand Journal of Ecology* 28(1): 151-159.
- Ward DF, Leschen RAB, Buckley TR 2015. More from ecologists to support natural history museums. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 30(7): 373-374.
- Watt JC 1962. Coleoptera from Hen Island (Taranga), Northland, New Zealand. *Records of the Auckland Institute and Museum* 5: 255-269.
- Watt JC 1974. Chalcodryidae: a new family of heteromorous beetles (Coleoptera: Tenebrionoidea). *Journal of the Royal Society of New Zealand* 4(1): 19-38.
- Watt JC 1975a. A general introduction to terrestrial Arthropoda of the Kermadec Islands. *New Zealand Entomologist* 6(1): 32-45.
- Watt JC 1975b. The terrestrial insects. In: Kuschel G ed. *Biogeography and Ecology in New Zealand*. The Hague, Netherlands, Dr. W. Junk b.v. Publishers. Pp. 507-535.
- Watt JC 1977. Conservation and type localities of New Zealand Coleoptera, and notes on collectors 1770-1920 *Journal of the Royal Society of New Zealand* 7(1): 79-91.
- Watt JC 1982a. Terrestrial Arthropods from the Poor Knights Islands, New Zealand. *Journal of the Royal Society of New Zealand* 12(3): 283-320.
- Watt JC 1982b. New Zealand beetles. *New Zealand Entomologist* 7(3): 213-221.
- Watts C, Dopheide A, Holdaway R, Davis C, Wood J, Thornburrow D, Dickie IA 2019. DNA metabarcoding as a tool for invertebrate community monitoring: a case study comparison with conventional techniques. *Austral Entomology* 58(3): 675-686.
- Watts CH, Stringer I, Gibbs G 2012. Insect Conservation in New Zealand: An Historical Perspective. In: New T ed. *Insect Conservation: Past, Present and Prospects*. Dordrecht, Netherlands, Springer. Pp. 213-243.
- Wheeler Q 2010. What would NASA do? Mission-critical infrastructure for species exploration. *Systematics and Biodiversity* 8(1): 11-15.
- Wheeler QD 2008. Introductory: Toward the New Taxonomy. In: Wheeler QD ed. *The New Taxonomy*. Boca Raton, FL, CRC Press. Pp. 1-17.
- Wheeler QD, Raven PH, Wilson EO 2004. Taxonomy: Impediment or expedient? *Science* 303(5656): 285-285.
- Wilkinson SP, Gault AA, Welsh SA, Smith JP, David BO, Hicks AS, Fake DR, Suren AM, Shaffer MR, Jarman SN and others 2024. TICI: a taxon-independent community index for eDNA-based ecological health assessment. *Peerj* 12: e16963.
- Will KW, Mishler BD, Wheeler QD 2005. The perils of DNA barcoding and the need for integrative taxonomy. *Systematic Biology* 54(5): 844-851.
- Wipfler B, Pohl H, Yavorskaya MI, Beutel RG 2016. A review of methods for analysing insect structures - the role of morphology in the age of phylogenomics. *Current Opinion in Insect Science* 18: 60-68.
- Woodward TE 1954. New records and descriptions of Hemiptera-Heteroptera from the Three Kings Islands. *Records of the Auckland Institute and Museum* 4(4): 215-233.
- Wührl L, Pylatiuk C, Giersch M, Lapp F, von Rintelen T, Balke M, Schmidt S, Cerretti P, Meier R 2022. DiversityScanner: Robotic handling of small invertebrates with machine learning methods. *Molecular Ecology Resources* 22(4): 1626-1638.
- Zachos FE 2018. (New) Species concepts, species delimitation and the inherent limitations of taxonomy. *Journal of Genetics* 97(4): 811-815.
- Zachos FE 2022. Critique of Taxonomic Reason(ing) Nature's Joints in Light of an 'Honest' Species Concept and Kurt Hübner's Historicist Philosophy of Science. In: Wilkins JS, Zachos FE, Pavlinov IY ed. *Species Problems and Beyond: Contemporary Issues in Philosophy and Practice*. Boca Raton, FL, CRC Press. Pp. 315-353.